

EXPLORING SPECIFIC INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES THAT PROMOTE STUDENT'S ABILITY TO IDENTIFY KEY, PERSUASIVE, RELEVANT AND STRONG ARGUMENTS TO PROVIDE AN EFFECTIVE RESPONSE TO AN ACADEMIC IELTS ESSAY QUESTION

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Abstract

This action research aimed to investigate the efficacy of employing the Select-Order-Systematize (SOS) method and Triangulation-Degree-Actuality (TDA) system in developing academic writing skills, specifically in addressing IELTS essay questions. The study was conducted in an 11th-grade classroom where students were undergoing intensive preparation for the IELTS exam. Through qualitative and quantitative analyses of student performance and feedback, the research identified educational difficulties and designed a lesson plan targeting the analysis of essay questions and identification of relevant arguments. The lesson implementation involved concept-based learning, collaborative group work, and peer assessment. Assessment instruments included IELTS Writing band descriptors and checklists for self-regulation. Results indicated improvements in students' ability to unpack essay questions, select effective arguments, and provide logical development, thus contributing to the overarching goal of academic writing skill enhancement.

Keywords: Select-Order-Systematize (SOS) method, Triangulation-Degree-Actuality (TDA) system, Concept-based learning, Self-regulation Global thinking, feed-back, feed-forward system.

Introduction: Action research serves as a valuable approach for addressing educational challenges and improving teaching practices (Lewin, 1946). In this study, we focus on enhancing academic writing skills, particularly in addressing IELTS essay questions, through the implementation of targeted strategies and methods. The research question driving this investigation is: *How will the use of the SOS method and TDA contribute to the development of the ability to identify relevant, actual arguments for giving an effective answer to the IELTS essay question?*

Methodology: This action research was conducted in an 11th-grade classroom, where students were engaged in intensive preparation for the IELTS exam. The study involved qualitative analysis of student performance and feedback, as well as quantitative assessment using established criteria such as IELTS Writing band descriptors. The research cycle incorporated iterative planning, implementation, and reflection stages to refine teaching strategies and address identified difficulties.

Results: The implementation of the planned lesson, which focused on unpacking essay questions and selecting effective arguments, yielded promising results. Students demonstrated improved skills in analyzing essay prompts, identifying relevant arguments, and providing logical development in their writing. Peer assessment using IELTS Writing band descriptors and checklists facilitated self-regulation and identified areas for improvement.

Discussion: The findings highlight the effectiveness of employing the SOS method and TDA system in enhancing students' academic writing skills for IELTS preparation. Collaborative group work and peer assessment fostered a supportive learning environment conducive to skill development. Challenges encountered, such as difficulty in determining the significance of arguments, provided valuable insights for future iterations of the lesson.

Conclusion: Action research informed by the principles of the SOS method and TDA system offers a promising approach to improving academic writing skills for IELTS preparation. Continued refinement of teaching strategies and assessment methods based on iterative reflection and feedback is essential for sustained progress. The study underscores the importance of targeted interventions tailored to the specific needs of learners in addressing educational challenges.

Recommendations: Based on the findings of this study, recommendations for educators include:

- Incorporating concept-based learning approaches to enhance students' analytical skills.
- Facilitating collaborative group work and peer assessment to promote self-regulation and critical thinking.

Teacher's reflection on the lesson developed as part of the research

Planning

This lesson was designed in order to find answers to the research question of one of the cycles of the action research conducted in 11th grades, where intensive preparation for the IELTS exam is going on. The main objective of this cycle (the 3rd one within the ongoing AR) was to test techniques and strategies aimed at further development of academic writing skills. **The objective of the 3rd cycle helped to identify its research question:** *How will the use of the SOS method and TCA contribute to the development of the ability to identify relevant, actual arguments for giving an effective answer to the IELTS essay question?*

Analysis and reflection on the two lessons of this research cycle, as well as a qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data obtained during interviews and questionnaires, made it possible to identify a number of educational difficulties and determine the objectives of the planned lesson. Most of all, I was interested in the following educational difficulties: *insufficient level of horizons in the framework of global, national changes,*

and the inability to determine the degree of relevancy and actuality of the arguments for an effective presentation of reasoning. These difficulties formed the basis of the learning objectives of the planned lesson:

- *analysis and unpacking IELTS essay question;*
- *identification relevant, actual and convincing arguments.*

Hypothetically, the tasks set for the planned lesson should also have contributed to the development of research skills and global thinking. That's what I was going to trace and study in the planned lesson, and give an evaluation of the techniques that I selected for the implementation of the tasks. Also, I was in the quest for answers for **the key AR question:** *What techniques and strategies will allow to give an effective answer to the IELTS academic question?* The rationale for choosing of the research question was a number of issues and challenges related to the level of development of students' academic writing skills. During the course of the action research, it was revealed that this language aspect tests a large number of skills, both explicit and implicit. The analytical work carried out made it possible to determine and formulate **the goal of professional development:** *Development of academic writing skills through express-and micro-analysis of the essay question and task.*

The expected **learning outcomes** of the planned lesson were:

- *students will be able to analyze and unpack the question of the academic essay and give a relevant, logical answer.*

While elaborating the lesson, I identified that the strategy of *express-, and micro-analysis* of the IELTS essay question will allow to work out the skill of unpacking essay question, and give a relevant and effective answer, meeting the requirements of the Task response criterion. The second expected result of the lesson reflects another important evaluation criterion - to present effective arguments and give them a logical development. This requirement reflects the Coherence and Cohesion criterion. In the course of checking the written work of students, it turned out to be the most challenging to achieve for most of my students.

Searching for answers to these learning difficulties and the literature review, as well as consulting with an IELTS international expert, allowed me to establish that developing the ability to identify the most effective arguments and give them logical development will also contribute to the development of research skills and global thinking. Therefore, I planned to organize analytical and research work in this lesson to find and select relevant, actual arguments with the SOS method (select-order-systematize). Thus, I was able to plan the implementation of a technique that allows **integrating the objectives of this lesson with the subject of Global Perspectives**, where students learn to identify and study a series of reliable resources, and draw conclusions on their reliability. I decided to organize mixed group work where collaborative work will aid in selecting the most relevant, actual and effective arguments.

For realizing objectives of the lesson, **Concept-based learning approach** was the most relevant and valuable. The concept "Perception", which is one of the

sub-concepts of the curriculum was suitable for studying essay - *Problem and solution*. According to my observations, this type of essay is relevant to the tasks of almost all school subjects: it raises a problematic issue and requires a reasoned explanation for its existence, its causes and consequences. Thus, I decided that Problem and Solution essay would create an adaptive environment for the development of academic writing skills.

The methods and techniques of the designed lesson, which were aimed at finding answers to the research question of the 3rd cycle, were determined as follows:

1. *Macro-, and micro-analysis of the academic essay question (Problem and Solution).*

2. *SOS and TDA methods: selection and evaluation of the degree of the arguments relevancy and their persuasiveness, and their ranking from less to more significant.*

In order to develop the ability to assess the degree of the arguments' relevancy, I developed the **TDA system:** **T** stands for **Triangulation** (3 reliable sources), **D** - **Degree of an Argument Relevancy**, **A** - **Actuality** (hereinafter **TDA**). The significance and benefits of this technique was assessed in previous years. It promotes the development of critical thinking skills and value judgment. The implementation of this technique was planned through **peer assessment**; thus, students would evaluate the selected arguments of students from opposite teams.

Educational resources have been selected taking into account the latest global trends in preparation for the international IELTS exam. Also, I decided to provide my students with the checklists created by me thanks to the research works of the previous years.

The essay question was: *Nowadays, certain problems are rising because of rising in number of citizens in the major towns of the world. Discuss about the issues and solutions to overcome it.*

The learning product of the planned lesson was writing of one body paragraph of the Problem and Solution essay. Learners could choose to write body paragraph Problem, or body paragraph Solution. This way, I decided to realize **Differentiation by task**.

I assumed that writing one body paragraph would provide an opportunity to track the effectiveness of the tasks of the planned lesson, evaluate the productivity of the selected techniques and strategies, and allow finding an answer to the research question.

TEACHING

The task of the initial stage of the lesson was directed on development of the skill of unpacking of the IELTS academic essay question (Problem and Solution). The use of macro- and micro-analysis of a series of questions of this type of essay created a condition when it was possible to trace the confident ability of my students to unpack and determine the big and narrow topic of the essay questions. *The development of this skill was assessed as formative:* students in pairs analyzed essay questions, defining big topic and narrow topic.

The next stage of the lesson, where the objective was to develop the ability to identify relevant, effective arguments and give them a logical development, was

fundamental, and should have answered to the research question of the 3rd cycle of AR. *How will the use of the SOS method and TDA contribute to the development of the ability to identify relevant, actual arguments to effectively answer an IELTS essay question?*

During this stage of the lesson, I was able to test the research skills of my students and the ability to select and critically evaluate data from reliable sources (.edu, .gov, .mil). Working in groups, during the discussion, students selected the most optimal arguments on the issue raised in the essay question through the lens of the concept *Perception* using the method SOS (select-order-systematize). At this stage, it was possible to trace the confident work of students with resources, the ability to determine how actual they are and relevant to the essay question. The arguments selected by the students were subjected to further selection and critical analysis in the framework of mutual assessment, where the task was to determine the 3 most effective and convincing arguments. To implement mutual evaluation, we used the TDA system as a criterion for evaluating the work done. Two groups of students successfully coped with the task: in the course of assessment by the general decision of the class, the arguments were assessed as actual, relevant and convincing. The third group was less successful. As it turned out during the feedback, it was easy for students to select relevant arguments, but it was difficult to determine the degree of their effectiveness. As a result, the degree of two arguments out of the three selected by the students lost their effectiveness, since these arguments did not make it possible to answer the essay question effectively. The circumstance with the learning difficulty provided an opportunity to organize a useful discussion, where I explained that IELTS essay requires demonstration of thinking on a global level, and arguments should be based on globally significant facts. The reason for the current difficulty was the inability to determine and differentiate the level of the problem: *local, national and global*. As a result, in the course of the lesson, I revealed this learning difficulty, and decided to take advantage of this; thus, the difficulty was set as a learning objective for the next classes.

At the next stage, the students ranked the selected arguments from the most to the least effective. When planning the lesson, I assumed that this task would cause difficulties. Indeed, in the course of completing the task, a situation arose in the lesson when the variety of mental approaches of my students became a stumbling block: some students determined the significance and effectiveness of some arguments, while others believed that the significance of the arguments was not high. The situation prompted me to remind students again about the format for determining the degree of importance of the problem, based on the system: *local problem - national problem - global problem*. Thus, it became easier for students to determine the degree of the arguments' effectiveness when they started to appeal to differentiating of issues according the level of their scale: local, national, global. As students worked in a team, it was difficult to track the readiness of each student to determine the degree of effectiveness of the arguments, and rank them in terms of importance.

However, it gave me the opportunity to see what actions I could take to enable each student to develop this skill in following lessons.

The planned educational product - writing a body paragraph Problem and Solution was obtained. My students used the selected and ranked arguments and wrote one body paragraph problem/solution according IELTS Writing band descriptors WT 2. Peer-assessment of the written paragraphs in accordance with the main essay criterion Task response allowed students to track and evaluate the ability of classmates to give a relevant answer to an essay question based on actual and effective arguments. In the format of the *feed-back, feed-forward system*, the students gave feedback and suggested steps to improve the skills to present effective arguments with their logical development.

Feedback from students at the end of the lesson made it possible to verify the value and significance of the goals and objectives of the lesson. Students appreciated the practical value of being able to identify effective arguments, and rank them from most to less significant. I received a number of answers to research question, and also, identified the reasons for students' difficulty in choosing relevant and effective arguments.

ASSESSMENT

The following assessment instruments were used in the planned lesson:

1. IELTS *Writing band descriptors* for assessing a written body paragraph. In this lesson, it was used for peer assessment of the Problem and Solution essay paragraph. The skill to unpack band descriptors, which were developed in the first term, enabled students to confidently follow the criteria of the Task response.

2. Checked-list for Problem and Solution essay, served as supporting learning material, as well as the resource for *self-assessment*. The checklists were elaborated to develop self-regulation skills and create conditions where the student can self-assess and self-edit a written work. Thus, the use of the Problem and Solution essay checklist enabled students to confidently construct a relevant body paragraph. The criterion of Coherence and Cohesion was also achieved due to the implementation and testing of the task designed for the lesson: "Identify relevant, actual and convincing arguments".

At the stage of mutual assessment of the written paragraphs, students gave feedback in the format of the *feed-back, feed-forward system*. It allowed to determine the area for improvement. The organization of this assessment system in the lesson allows students, in the course of feedback to each other, to identify possible causes of personal learning difficulties, and determine further steps to eliminate them.

To determine the degree of effectiveness of the selected arguments, the students used the TDA techniques, which again proved its value. *TDA contributes to the development of the ability to identify relevant, actual arguments for giving an effective answer to the IELTS essay question. That was observed during the lesson.*

As a result, the selected methods and assessment strategies made it possible to implement the tasks set. I

identified the learning difficulty, which impeded to academic writing skills improvement, and got a number of answers to the key research question “*What methods and strategies allow giving an effective answer to the IELTS essay question?*”

EVALUATION

The goals and objectives of the lessons in grade 11, respectively, are aimed at developing the skills for the successful passing of IELTS exam. The study of students' written works and the analysis of their learning difficulties allowed determining the research question of the 3rd cycle of action research: *How will the use of the SOS method and TDA contribute to the development of the ability to identify relevant, actual arguments for giving an effective answer to the IELTS essay question?* The objectives of the designed lesson were derived from the research question itself.

When planning the lesson, I assumed that the objectives of the lesson will:

- enable students to more confidently unpack IELTS academic essay questions;
- contribute to the development of the ability to determine effective, relevant arguments for the IELTS essay question through the SOS method and TDA, which in turn should have contributed to the development of global thinking and research skills.

The lesson was aimed at finding answers on the research question of the 3rd cycle, and also, should have given answers to the key research question. The identified learning objectives, and the selected techniques, methods and approaches, have become effective within the framework of the lesson.

First, allowed to identify the cause of the difficulty with the ability to identify relevant and effective arguments. The reason, as it turned out, is the inability to determine and differentiate the level of the problem - whether it is local, national or global. The circumstance made it possible to organize a discussion, which had a positive impact on the further educational process. In addition, it made it possible to identify one of the educational difficulties of individual students, which prevented the development of academic writing skills. I decided to investigate the causes of this difficulty in the next cycle of ongoing action research. *Second*, the use of the SOS method contributes to the selection of relevant, actual arguments, which in turn makes it possible to effectively answer IELTS essay question. *Third*, testing the TCA technique gave my students the opportunity evaluate effectiveness of the collected arguments, then, rank them from the most to the least significant. Moreover, the selected assessment strategies and techniques provided an opportunity to develop critical thinking skills, and can be considered valuable, long-term and perspective. What is more, it was possible to trace the level of my students' satisfaction with their learning needs. They found out how to give an effective answer to the IELTS essay question.

What made it difficult to conduct this lesson, and what changes would I make?

First, use the possibilities of GOOGLE drive in order to create a bank of selected, effective arguments.

This way, the collaboration of all 11 graders will give opportunity to create a learning resource with effective arguments on Common IELTS topics (via eliciting big actual concepts). Second, elicit a concept from essay question itself, instead of linking the essay macro-topic to the one of the sub concepts of the curriculum.

What techniques can I suggest to colleagues?

First, develop the skill of the essay question unpacking through *macro and micro analysis*. Secondly, develop the ability to select relevant arguments, and the ability to rank the selected arguments in terms of importance (from least to the most significant), because it make it possible to give a relevant and effective answer to the question of an academic essay.

The ongoing research made it possible to determine the specific causes of personalized difficulties of some of my students. The findings of the research and elaborated techniques aided to develop writing academic skills. Thus, these students in the summative works demonstrated the optimal level of academic writing skills, effectively answering the essay question.

- Utilizing digital tools such as Google Drive to create shared resources for effective argument selection and evaluation.
- Eliciting concepts directly from essay questions to foster deeper understanding and relevance in lesson planning.

Future Directions: Future research endeavors should focus on:

- Investigating the long-term impact of action research interventions on academic writing proficiency.
- Exploring additional strategies and techniques for addressing specific challenges in IELTS essay writing.
- Extending the scope of inquiry to include diverse learner populations and educational contexts for broader generalization of findings.

References

1. Lewin, K. (1946). Action research and minority problems. *Journal of Social Issues*, 2(4), 34-46.
2. Goldsmith, M. (2003). Try feedforward instead of feedback. *Journal for Quality and Participation*, 38-40.
3. C. Little, C., “Designing and Implementing Concept-Based Curriculum”, In Tan, L. (Ed.)
4. Curriculum for High Ability Learners (L. Tan, ed.), pp. 43-59, Singapore: Springer Nature, 2017 H. Erickson, Concept-based teaching and learning. IB position paper. The Hague: International Baccalaureate Organisation, 2012. Retrieved from http://www.ibmidatlantic.org/Concept_Based_Teaching_Learning.pdf
5. H. Erickson, Concept-based teaching and learning. IB position paper. The Hague: International Baccalaureate Organisation, 2012. Retrieved from http://www.ibmidatlantic.org/Concept_Based_Teaching_Learning.pdf
6. L. Omer, “Successful scientific instruction involves more than just discovering concepts through inquiry-based activities”, in *Education*, vol. 3, pp. 18-32, 2002